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**Un intervento di coaching infermieristico per pazienti con
scompenso cardiaco: uno studio di fattibilità**

Ines Basso

Patterns of self-care and clinical events in a cohort of adults with heart failure: 1 year follow-up

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ABSTRACT

Background: Heart failure (HF) self-care is important in reducing clinical events (all-cause mortality, emergency room visits and hospitalizations). HF self-care behaviors are multidimensional and include maintenance (i.e. daily adherence behaviors), management (i.e. symptom response behaviors) and consulting behaviors (i.e. contacting a provider when appropriate). Across these dimensions, patterns of successful patient engagement in self-care have been observed (e.g. successful in one dimension but not in others), but no previous studies have linked patterns of HF self-care to clinical events.

Objectives: To identify patterns of self-care behaviors in HF patients and their association with clinical events.

Methods: This was a prospective, non-experimental, cohort study. Community-dwelling HF patients (n = 459) were enrolled across Italy, and clinical events were collected one year after enrollment. We measured dimensions of self-care behavior with the Self-Care of HF Index (maintenance, management, and confidence) and the European HF Self-care Behavior Scale (consulting behaviors). We used latent class mixture modeling to identify patterns of HF self-care across dimensions, and Cox proportional hazards modeling to quantify event-free survival over 12 months of follow-up.

Results: Patients (mean age 71.8 ± 12.1 years) were mostly males (54.9%). Three patterns of self-care behavior were identified; we labeled each by their most prominent dimensional characteristic: poor symptom response, good symptom response, and maintenance-focused behaviors. Patients with good symptom response behaviors had fewer clinical events compared with those who had poor symptom response behaviors (adjusted hazard ratio = 0.66 [0.46–0.96], p = 0.03). Patients with poor symptom response behaviors had the most frequent clinical events. Patients with poor symptom response and those with maintenance-focused behaviors had a similar frequency of clinical events.

Conclusions: Self-care is significantly associated with clinical events. Routine assessment, mitigation of barriers, and interventions targeting self-care are needed to reduce clinical events in HF patients.

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Società Italiana di Cardiologia

LA SOCIETÀ DELLE TRE ANIME

C.S. Lee et al. / Heart & Lung 47 (2018) 40–46

Dopo un anno di follow-up:

- 30% dei pazienti deceduti
- 30% è stato ricoverato o ha avuto un accesso in pronto soccorso

Effects of nurse-led self-care interventions on health outcomes among people with heart failure: A systematic review and meta-analysis

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(a)

Study	Self care			Usual care		
	Total	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD
Chew et al. (2021)	62	-26.90	24.9000	58	-24.00	22.0000
Clark et al. (2015)	25	62.61	21.8000	25	60.43	24.1200
Dekker et al. (2012)	21	-42.00	6.0000	20	-58.00	5.0000
Ilaslan & Özer (2021)	32	-40.05	27.6300	32	-88.98	19.2500
Jiang et al. (2021) A	57	-22.24	14.9300	60	-33.88	19.0400
Jiang et al. (2021) B	60	-20.04	15.5000	60	-33.88	19.0400
Koberich et al. (2015)	58	69.38	18.8600	52	59.03	21.2500
Leavitt et al. (2020)	19	-28.94	18.0800	21	-55.12	26.6600
Lundgren et al. (2016)	25	-35.80	15.3000	25	-45.30	21.3000
Otsu & Moriyama (2011)	49	6.65	0.6100	47	6.29	0.4800
Sadeghi Akbari et al. (2019)	35	-45.20	8.3000	35	-66.80	15.4000
Saleh et al. (2022)	65	79.00	22.9600	67	63.00	27.4000
Wang et al. (2017)	31	-20.74	14.6600	31	-35.29	13.6700
D. S. Yu et al. (2015)	70	-29.90	16.5000	50	-41.30	22.4000
D. S. Yu et al. (2022)	115	-18.77	13.3100	113	-23.68	18.2700
M. Yu et al. (2015)	75	-7.70	11.5000	75	-15.80	11.1000
Random effects model	799			771		
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 84\%$, $t^2 = 0.3798$, $p < 0.01$						

quality of life (a)

(b)

Study	Usual care			Self care		
	Total	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD
Chang et al. (2016)	41	6.54	3.9200	43	4.09	3.2000
Jiang et al. (2021) A	60	4.21	3.7500	57	3.06	3.8000
Jiang et al. (2021) B	60	4.21	3.7500	60	3.67	3.4900
Nahlen Bose et al. (2016)	50	4.50	3.5700	44	4.37	4.2700
M. Yu et al. (2015)	75	3.60	3.3000	75	1.30	1.9000
Random effects model	286			279		
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 60\%$, $t^2 = 0.6030$, $p = 0.04$						

anxiety (b)

(c)

Study	Usual care			Self care		
	Total	Mean	SD	Total	Mean	SD
Clark et al. (2015)	25	-63.96	26.9800	25	-64.08	24.3100
Graven et al. (2022)	23	2.65	1.8200	19	2.15	1.7900
Ilaslan & Özer (2021)	32	1.84	0.5100	32	0.92	0.5600
Saleh et al. (2022)	67	116.00	28.3800	65	89.00	26.2700
Shao et al. (2013)	46	5.87	3.2800	47	3.04	1.9800
Random effects model	193			188		
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 82\%$, $t^2 = 0.3525$, $p < 0.01$						

symptom burden (c)

(d)

Study	Self care		Usual care		Risk Ratio	RR	95%-CI	Weight
	Events	Total	Events	Total				
Boyde et al. (2018)	13	100	14	100	0.93	0.93	[0.46; 1.87]	12.3%
Chew et al. (2021)	13	70	15	72	0.89	0.89	[0.46; 1.73]	13.7%
Leavitt et al. (2020)	3	19	6	21	0.55	0.55	[0.16; 1.91]	4.0%
Schmaderer et al. (2021) A	13	23	13	26	1.13	1.13	[0.67; 1.91]	22.0%
Schmaderer et al. (2021) B	4	25	13	26	0.32	0.32	[0.12; 0.85]	6.4%
Young et al. (2016)	12	51	12	47	0.92	0.92	[0.46; 1.85]	12.6%
D. S. Yu et al. (2015)	25	90	27	88	0.91	0.91	[0.57; 1.43]	29.0%
Random effects model		378		380	0.88	0.88	[0.68; 1.12]	100.0%
Heterogeneity: $I^2 = 0\%$, $t^2 < 0.0001$, $p = 0.47$								

hospital readmission (d)

Non-invasive home telemonitoring in patients with decompensated heart failure: a systematic review and meta-analysis

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Table 4 All-cause hospitalizations (TM vs. UC)

Study or subgroup	TM Events	TM Total	UC Events ²	UC Total ²	Weight	Risk ratio M-H, random	Risk ratio CI start	Risk ratio CI end
Antonicelli 2008	9	28	26	29	3.89	0.36	0.21	0.62
Chaudhry 2010	407	826	392	827	17.24	1.04	0.94	1.15
Cleland 2005	155	168	69	85	16.76	1.14	1.02	1.27
Comin-Colet 2016	20	81	45	97	5.56	0.53	0.34	0.82
Dar 2009	44	91	39	91	8.36	1.13	0.82	1.55
Dendale 2012	64	80	66	80	15.09	0.97	0.84	1.13
Kotooka 2018	27	92	34	91	5.99	0.79	0.52	1.19
Ong 2016	363	715	355	722	17.09	1.03	0.93	1.15
Weintraub 2010	51	95	49	93	10.01	1.02	0.78	1.33
Total	1140	2176	1075	2115	100	0.95	0.84	1.08
Heterogeneity					Test for overall effect			
Tau ²	χ^2	df	P	I ²	Z	P		
0.02	29.31	8	0.0003	73	0.78	0.43		

Studio INTERCOACH

Un intervento di coaching infermieristico con tele-
monitoraggio domiciliare: uno studio di fattibilità

Obiettivi

Obiettivo primario: Valutare la fattibilità e l'accettazione di un intervento di coaching infermieristico con tele-monitoraggio domiciliare.

Obiettivo secondario: esplorare la fattibilità di un RCT per valutarne l'efficacia

Setting: Azienda Ospedaliera Universitaria Maggiore della Carità di Novara

SCDU Cardiologia 1

SCDU Medicina Interna 1

SCDU Medicina Interna 2

Criteria di inclusione:

- Pazienti ricoverati per scompenso cardiaco
- FE conservata o ridotta
- Dimessi al domicilio

Criteria di esclusione:

- MMSE \leq 24
- Non in grado di comprendere lingua italiana o seguire il protocollo
- Seguiti da altri servizi sanitari

Fase 1: Incontro educativo pre-dimissione

- *Educazione terapeutica:*
 - Temi prioritari per rimanere in salute
 - Riconoscimento sintomi
 - Gestione terapia
- *Identificazione e condivisione obiettivi prioritari e la motivazione al cambiamento* (Prochaska & Di Clemente, 1982)
- *Addestramento all'utilizzo del sistema di tele-monitoraggio*

Fase 2: Coaching telefonico infermieristico

Fase 3: Tele-monitoraggio da remoto

In caso di alterazione dei parametri vitali

Senza sintomi
(Punteggio ESAS ≤ 4)

Rinforzo interventi self-management
Rinvio al MMG se persistenza alterazioni ≥ 3 giorni

Con sintomi moderati
(Punteggio ESAS 5-7)

Valutazione/consulenza del medico ospedaliero del servizio dal quale l'assistito è stato dimesso

Con sintomi severi
(Punteggio ESAS ≥ 8)

Rinvio al servizio di emergenza territoriale

Outcomes dello studio

A new framework for developing and evaluating complex interventions: update of Medical Research Council guidance

Kathryn Skivington,¹ Lynsay Matthews,¹ Sharon Anne Simpson,¹ Peter Craig,¹ Janis Baird,² Jane M Blazeby,³ Kathleen Anne Boyd,⁴ Neil Craig,⁵ David P French,⁶ Emma McIntosh,⁴ Mark Petticrew,⁷ Jo Rycroft-Malone,⁸ Martin White,⁹ Laurence Moore¹

- Vulnerabilità degli assistiti
- Multidisciplinarietà dell'approccio
- Personalizzazione e flessibilità dell'intervento
- Esperienza e competenza richiesti all'infermiere coach
- Setting diversi

Conclusioni

- Necessità di rispondere alle nuove esigenze del SSN
- Evoluzione della Professione Infermieristica
- Studi multi professionali/multi disciplinari

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